

PATTERNS AND RISK FACTORS OF SUICIDAL BEHAVIOR IN PATIENTS OF GERONTOPSYCHIATRIC UNITS

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ABSTRACT: Relevance. Suicidal behaviors in elderly patients with various mental disorders are common and represent a significant challenge in gerontopsychiatric care, affecting prognosis and quality of life. Purpose. To investigate the clinical and pathokinetic characteristics of suicidal behaviors in elderly psychiatric patients, identify risk factors, and improve preventive and therapeutic interventions. Materials and Methods. The study included 62 patients aged 55-75 years admitted to a regional psychiatric hospital. Suicidal behaviors were assessed using the Suicide Ideation Scale (SSI) and Pierce Suicide Intent Scale (PSIS). Affective disorders were evaluated using the Montgomery-Asberg Depression Scale (MADS) and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI). Results. On the SSI scale, moderate and high suicide risk was observed in 64,5% of patients. Self-poisoning was the most common suicide attempt method (35,49%), followed by self-cutting (25,8%), self-harm by injury (19,3%), and height-related attempts (13%). Women more frequently chose self-poisoning (50,4%). Anxiety-depressive symptoms were significant contributors to suicidal behavior. Among mental pathologies, organic mental disorders and affective disorders carried the highest suicide risk. Conclusion. The findings highlight the importance of early identification and individualized intervention for suicidal elderly patients, improving the effectiveness of gerontopsychiatric care and suicide prevention strategies.

Keywords: gerontopsychiatry, suicidal behavior, anxiety, depression, affective disorders.

ГЕРОНТОПСИХИАТРИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ И ФАКТОРЫ РИСКА СУИЦИДАЛЬНОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ

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АННОТАЦИЯ: Актуальность. В геронтопсихиатрическом отделении широко встречаются суицидальные действия на фоне различных психических патологий, что делает задачу их профилактики и повышения эффективности лечения особенно актуальной. Цель. Изучить клинико-психопатологические и патокинетические особенности суицидального поведения у пациентов геронтопсихиатрического отделения, выявить факторы риска и повысить эффективность профилактических мероприятий. Материалы и методы. В исследование включены 62 пациента в возрасте 55-75 лет. Суицидальные действия оценивались с помощью Suicide Ideation Scale (SSI) и Pierce Suicide Intent Scale (PSIS), а аффективные расстройства - с помощью Montgomery-Asberg Depression Scale (MADS) и Beck Depression Inventory (BDI). Результаты. По шкале SSI средний и высокий уровень риска суицида был выявлен у 64,5% пациентов. Наиболее часто использовался метод самоотравления (35,49%), затем - порезы (25,8%), удушение (19,3%) и прыжки с высоты (13%). У женщин чаще встречалось самоотравление (50,4%). При суицидальном поведении значительную роль играют тревожно-депрессивные симптомы. Наибольший риск суицида наблюдался при органических психических и аффективных расстройствах. Вывод. Результаты исследования позволяют повысить эффективность психиатрической помощи пациентам пожилого возраста с риском суицида в геронтопсихиатрических отделениях, включая раннее выявление риска и целенаправленную профилактику.

Ключевые слова: геронтопсихиатрия, суицидальное поведение, тревога, депрессия, аффективные расстройства.

GERONTOPSIXIATRIYA BO‘LIMI BEMORLARIDA SUISIDAL XATTI-HARAKATLARINING XUSUSIYATLARI VA XAVF OMILLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA: Dolzarblik. Gerontopsixiatriya bo‘limida turli ruhiy patologiyalar fonida suisidal xatti-harakatlari keng uchrab, ularning oldini olish va davolash samaradorligini oshirish dolzarb vazifa hisoblanadi. Maqsad. Gerontopsixiatriya bo‘limidagi bemorlarda suisidal xatti-harakatlarining kliniko-psixopatologik va patokinetik xususiyatlarini o‘rganish, risk omillarini aniqlash va profilaktik choralarning samaradorligini oshirish. Materiallar va usullar. Tadqiqotga 55-75 yoshdagi 62 nafar bemor kiritildi. O‘zini o‘ldirish xatti-harakatlari Suicide Ideation Scale (SSI) va Pierce Suicide Intent Scale (PSIS) yordamida baholandi hamda Affective Disorderlar Montgomery-Asberg Scale (MADS) va Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) orqali o‘rganildi. Natijalar. SSI skalasida o‘rtacha va yuqori darajadagi suisidal xatti-harakatlar xavfi 64,5% bemorlarda aniqlangan. O‘zini zaharlash eng ko‘p ishlatiladigan usul bo‘lib (35,49%), undan keyin o‘zini kesish (25,8%), o‘zini ochish (19,3%) va balandlikdan tushish (13%) keladi. Ayollarda o‘zini zaharlash ko‘proq uchraydi (50,4%). O‘zini o‘ldirish xatti-harakatlarida xavotir-depressiv simptomlar muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Organik ruhiy va affektiv buzilishlar eng yuqori o‘zini o‘ldirish xavfiga ega. Xulosa. Tadqiqot natijalari qariyalar psixiatriya bo‘limlarida o‘zini o‘ldirish xavfi bo‘lgan bemorlarga ko‘rsatiladigan psixiatriya yordamini samaradorligini oshirishga imkon beradi, shu jumladan xavfni erta aniqlash va profilaktik choralarga yo‘naltirish.

Kalit so‘zlar: gerontopsixiatriya, suisidal xatti-harakatlari, xavotir, depressiya, affektiv buzilishlar.

Introduction. Suicide represents a significant public health challenge worldwide, with the World Health Organization reporting over one million deaths annually due to self-harm. In recent decades, our country has demonstrated elevated suicide rates, exceeding 20 cases per 100,000 population. Individuals exhibiting severe forms of suicidal behavior or identified as high-risk require continuous psychiatric supervision in specialized inpatient facilities. Treatment often involves restrictive measures when patients pose an immediate threat to their own life or the lives of others [1–5]. Therapeutic interventions targeting psychopathological symptoms aim to stabilize mental health and mitigate suicidal ideation. Nevertheless, high-risk patients may still attempt suicide during hospitalization, on therapeutic leave, or shortly after discharge [6–9].

Historically, the evolution of psychiatric care has progressively improved patient quality of life, contributing to a reduction in suicidal behaviors and mortality within psychiatric institutions. While psychiatric facilities in the 9th century primarily provided custodial care, by the early 20th century, structured diagnostic and therapeutic approaches-including interventions for depressive disorders-were introduced alongside inpatient and outpatient care systems [10–16]. Consequently, although mortality rates in psychiatric hospitals are now lower than in the past, suicides continue to occur [17–19].

Previously, suicide attempts and completed suicides within psychiatric hospitals were not systematically recorded; some patients died in general medical facilities, while others were classified as accidental deaths. Despite this, the frequency of suicidal behavior serves as a key indicator of psychiatric care quality [20–23]. Annual reports suggest that approximately 10% of inpatient suicides occur in psychiatric clinics, representing 2.5% of all suicides in the general population [24]. Internationally, legal claims against psychiatric institutions following patient suicides are common. Courts often hold inpatient facilities to a higher standard of oversight due to the controlled environment, linking accountability to

suicide prevention. In the United States, suicide rates are a critical parameter for hospital accreditation through the Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations (JCAHO). Suicides within psychiatric hospitals are considered “sentinel events,” signaling the need for prompt investigation and response. However, not all sentinel events result from medical error, and not all errors necessitate formal review [25–28].

In older adults, suicide rates are approximately three times higher than among young individuals aged 15–24, with a particularly heightened risk in men [29]. Advancing age often entails loss of loved ones, declining social roles, and deteriorating physical health. Reduced adaptive capacity makes older adults more vulnerable to environmental changes, social misunderstandings, and feelings of frustration. The presence of depressive disorders in this population further elevates suicide risk, emphasizing the importance of continued research into late-life suicidal behavior.

Purpose of the study. The research aimed to enhance psychiatric care for patients in gerontopsychiatric hospitals who exhibit suicidal behaviors across various mental disorders.

Materials and methods. The study examined 62 patients aged 55–75 admitted to the Smolensk Regional Clinical Psychiatric Hospital. Patient registration was completed within 48 hours of admission, corresponding to the early post-admission period for those with a recent suicide attempt. Suicidal behaviors were assessed using the Suicide Ideation Scale (SSI) and Pierce Suicide Intent Scale (PSIS). Affective disorders were evaluated with the Montgomery-Asberg Depression Rating Scale (MADRS) and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI).

Results and discussion. The study analyzed the clinical and psychopathological characteristics of internal suicidal behaviors, identifying the factors and severity of suicide risk in relation to specific mental disorders. The psychological profile of suicidal patients was constructed considering the dynamics of behavior before and after a suicide attempt.

Analysis of psychometric assessments revealed prominent anxiety-depressive symptoms. On the MADRS, scores of 20-39, indicative of moderate to severe depression, were found in 64,5% of patients. Objective depressive symptoms were observed in 90,3% of participants, whereas only 54,8% reported subjective depressive feelings. Nearly half of the patients experienced difficulty in active participation, while every second patient reported internal tension and sleep disturbances. Approximately two-thirds occasionally or continuously expressed pessimistic or suicidal thoughts. Anxiety was present in 58% of patients, confirming the predominance of anxiety-depressive syndromes. The authors categorized these disorders as depressive, depressive-hypochondriacal, depressive-paranoid, and high-risk disturbing-depressive patterns, highlighting the need for combined psychopharmacological and psychocorrective interventions to prevent recurrence.

On the SSI scale, scores corresponding to average and high suicide risk (10-25.,8) were found in 64,5% of patients. A desire to attempt suicide was reported by 38,7% of patients. The BDI revealed that 74,2% of participants experienced suicidal thoughts without intent to act, while 16% expressed active suicidal intent. Pierce’s Suicide Intent Scale indicated that over half (64,5%) of respondents were convinced that the method they chose would result in death.

Analysis of suicide attempt methods demonstrated a statistically significant preference for self-poisoning (35,49%, $p < 0,005$), whereas self-burning and electrocution were rare (5,9% each). Intermediate methods included self-cutting (25,8%), self-harm by exposure (19,3%), and jumps from heights (13%). Gender differences were observed: women predominantly used self-poisoning (50,4%),

typically via medication, while men employed self-poisoning (23,4%), self-injection (23,5%), and sapophoresis (29,4%) with roughly equal frequency. Falls from heights were chosen by 21,4% of women and 5,9% of men, and electrocution or spontaneous flooding methods were reported exclusively in men. Overall, men tended to select more violent and traumatic methods, often resulting in complex post-attempt periods requiring somatic medical care.

Most suicide attempts occurred during evening or nighttime hours (71%), likely associated with exacerbation of anxiety and depressive symptoms in patients with exogenous, organic, or vascular affective disorders.

Detailed analysis of suicide attempt methods allows predicting both the dynamics and severity of suicide risk. The motives for suicide attempts were distributed as follows: protest or retaliation in 13% of cases, calling for help or seeking mercy in 35,5%, avoiding suffering or punishment in 9,7%, and resignation to life in 32,2% of cases. Both men and women critically assessed their suicide attempts. Half of the cases involved critical or manipulative forms of post-suicide behavior, with gender differences observed in the remaining cases: 22,6% of women exhibited manipulative post-suicide behaviors, often resulting in repeated suicide attempts.

The study confirmed the significant role of anxiety-depressive symptoms in suicidal behavior, highlighting the importance and severity of depressive disorders. In elderly patients with mental disorders, the suicide risk was found to be moderate to high. Contributing factors for the long-term and chronic course of suicidal behavior were identified. Typical manifestations of suicide attempts and internal suicidal behaviors were observed as suicidal thoughts, plans, and intent. The occurrence, progression, recurrence of suicidal behavior, and variations in the post-suicidal period in elderly patients were analyzed.

Conclusions. The findings provide evidence to improve the efficiency of geriatric psychiatric units in managing suicidal patients. While suicidal behaviors are equally observed in elderly men and women, men demonstrate a notably higher risk. Key factors increasing this risk include severe somatic illnesses and alcohol dependence. Among geriatric mental disorders, organic mental and affective disorders are associated with the highest suicide risk. Within affective disorders, depressive and anxiety symptoms are particularly critical. Anxiety, characterized by internal tension and discomfort, combined with sleep disturbances, may act as a trigger for translating internal suicidal thoughts into actual attempts. The heightened suicide risk in elderly psychiatric patients is linked to a stronger conviction about the lethality of the method and a greater intent to act on suicidal thoughts. These results support improvements in suicide prevention and early detection strategies in the elderly population.

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